

New 2,4-Disubstituted-3,5-dimethylpyrroles : Synthesis and Reactions

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The increasing interest in the chemistry of pyrrole besides its diverse biological activity¹, led us to report here the synthesis of some 2,4-disubstituted-3,5-dimethylpyrroles. The general scheme shown describes the different pathways applied in this work.

Results and Discussion

3,5-Dimethyl-2,4-pyrrole dicarboxhydrazide (1) was prepared via fusion of 2,4-dicarbethoxy-3,5-dimethylpyrrole² with hydrazine in a modification of the previously reported procedure of Fischer and Waibel³ which consists in heating the Knorr pyrrole² compound and hydrazine in an autoclave at 130° for 96 h. Reacting 1 with certain aldehydes afforded the corresponding diarylidene carboxhydrazides (2). Attempts to cyclise 2 to the corresponding 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives using acetic anhydride were unsuccessful. Interaction of the dicarboxhydrazide (1) with ethanolic CS₂/KOH on cold gave the di(potassium dithiocarbazate) which on reacting with hydrazine yielded 3 (Scheme 1) instead of the expected 2,4-[di(4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)]-3,5-dimethylpyrrole. Structure of the hydrazinothioxotriazole (3) was supported by compatible analytical and spectroscopic data. The ¹H nmr spectrum showed the disappearance of the two methyl groups of the pyrrole ring at δ 2.35–2.4 as well as the singlet signal at δ 11.7 ascribed to the NH pyrrole. Meanwhile, the spectrum complies with the assigned structure of 3. Additionally, the m.p. of the product 3 agreed well with the earlier report^{4,5} for 4-amino-3-hydrazino-5-thioxo-1,2,4-triazole (3) confirming the structure. For further confirmation, 3 was reacted with benzaldehyde to yield 4-benzylideneamino-3-benzylidenehydrazino-5-thioxo-1,2,4-triazole whose structure complies with the previously reported⁵ m.p. Also, the ir and the ¹H nmr JICS-8

Scheme 1

spectral data added further evidence to the assigned structure. A possible mechanism for the formation of 3 is shown in Chart 1.

A survey of the literature⁶ revealed that formation of aminotriazoles could be achieved through an alternative synthesis which consists in hydrazinolysis of oxadiazoles. Consequently, 1 was heated with ethanolic CS₂/KOH to yield the corresponding 2,4-dioxadiazolyl-3,5-dimethylpyrrole (4), which on reacting with hydrazine produced 5. For the confirmation of the structure of 4, it was alkylated with ethyl iodide to afford 2,4-[di(5-ethylthio-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)]-3,5-

Chart 1

dimethylpyrrole. It is to be mentioned that hydrazinolysis of 4 in different solvents was examined. Refluxing 4 with two moles of hydrazine in water⁶ gave a solution from which no product could be isolated. Meanwhile, the reaction products of 4 with hydrazine in absolute ethanol were found to be the starting material dioxadiazolyl derivative (4) as the major product together with 5 in a smaller ratio. Compound 4 was reacted further with acetic anhydride to get the corresponding acetyl derivative, whose structure was in accord with analytical and spectroscopic data (ir, ¹H nmr and mass). On the other hand, increasing the percentage yield of the desired triazolyl derivative (5) from 12 to 61% was accomplished by running the reaction in dry dioxane instead of ethanol. Augmenting the molar quantity of hydrazine to 5–7 moles in absolute ethanol or dioxane at longer reaction time produced 5 rather than the expected ditriazolyl deriva-

ive. The structure of 5 was chemically confirmed by reacting it with some aldehydes and benzoyl chloride to yield the corresponding Schiff bases (6) and amide (7) respectively.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on a Griffin apparatus and are uncorrected. Microanalysis and mass spectrum were carried out at the Microanalytical Center, University of Cairo, Egypt. Ir spectra (KBr) were determined on a Shimadzu IR 435 spectrophotometer. ¹H nmr spectra were performed in Faculty of Pharmacy, Cairo University, using a JEOL FXQ (90 MHz) spectrometer. Progress of the reaction was monitored by tlc (silica gel G, Merck, type 60⁺; benzene-acetone, 8 : 2).

2,4-Dicarbethoxy-3,5-dimethylpyrrole² and 4-benzylideneamino-3-benzylidenehydrazino-5-thioxo-1,2,4-triazole⁵ were prepared according to reported procedures.

3,5-Dimethyl-2,4-pyrrole dicarboxyhydrazide (1)³ : A mixture of 2,4-dicarbethoxy-3,5-dimethylpyrrole (23.9 g, 0.1 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (95%; 100 ml) was fused at 170° for 82 h. The residue was then triturated with ethanol, filtered and washed with ether to yield 1 (15 g, 71%), m.p. 262°d; ν_{max} 3 400 (NH pyrrole), 3 300–3 200 (NH, NH₂) and 1 650 cm^{-1} (C=O).

2,4-Di[N²-arylidene carboxyhydrazide]-3,5-dimethylpyrrole (2) : A mixture of 1 (0.31 g, 0.0015 mol) and the appropriate aldehyde (0.003 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and the separated solid was crystallised from methanol (yields 76–87%) (Table 1).

4-Amino-3-hydrazino-5-thioxo-1,2,4-triazole (3) : Carbon disulphide (2.28 g, 0.03 mol) was added dropwise to an ice-cold solution of 1 (2.11 g, 0.01 mol) and KOH (1.82 g, 0.032 mol) in absolute ethanol (40 ml). The mixture was diluted with ethanol (30 ml) and stirred at room temperature for 2 h. Dry ether (40 ml) was then added and the separated solid washed with ether (2 × 10 ml). The product obtained in nearly quantitative yield, was used as such in the next reaction. A

TABLE I - PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2 AND 4*

Compd. no.	R	M.p. °C	ν_{\max} (cm ⁻¹)	
			NH	CO
2a	C ₆ H ₅	278-80	3 300- 3 250	1 650
2b	3-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	284-86		
2c	4-Br-C ₆ H ₄	258-59		
2d	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	234-36	3 350- 3 250	1 640
2e	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	245-47		
2f	CH=CHC ₆ H ₅	260-62	3 350- 3 250	1 630
6a	C ₆ H ₅	240-42		3 300
6b	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	270-72		3 250

2c and 2f δ (DMSO-d₆) 2.35 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.8 (8H, m, ArH 2c) or 6.3-7.8 (14H, m, ArH and styryl protons), 8.2, (2H, d, 2 × CH=N 2f) or 8.6 (2H, s, 2 × CH=N 2c) and 11.0-11.7 (3H, br, NH pyrrole and 2 × CONH).

6a δ ((CD₃)₂CO) 2.35 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.9 (1H, br, SH), 7.4 (5H, m, ArH), 7.9 (1H, s, NH triazole), 8.6 (1H, s, N=CH) and 11.7 (1H, s, NH pyrrole).

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

suspension of this salt (2.2 g, 0.005 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (95%; 1 ml, 0.02 mol) was refluxed while stirring for 1 h. Cold water (5 ml) was then added and the mixture was neutralised with concentrated HCl. The separated solid was washed with cold water and crystallised from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 234°d (lit.⁵ 234°d) (Found : C, 16.6; H, 4.0; N, 57.0. C₂H₆N₆S calcd. for : C, 16.4; H, 4.1; N, 57.5%); ν_{\max} 3 250-3 100 cm⁻¹ (NH and NH₂); δ (DMSO-d₆) 4.9-5.2 (4H, m, 2 × NH₂), 6.8 (1H, s, NH of hydrazino) and 8.4 (1H, s, NH of triazole ring).

2,4-[Di(5-mercapto-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)]-3,5-dimethylpyrrole (4) : A mixture of 1 (10.33 g; 0.049 mol), KOH (5.58 g, 0.098 mol), CS₂ (8.36 g, 0.11 mol) and ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed for 24 h. The alcohol was then removed by distillation under diminished pressure, the residue was dissolved in water (200 ml) and the solution acidified with concentrated HCl.

The separated solid was washed with water and crystallised from dimethylformamide, m.p. 275°d (11 g, 76%) (Found : C, 40.7; H, 3.0; N, 23.2. C₁₀H₉O₂S₂ calcd. for : C, 40.6; H, 3.0; N, 23.7%); ν_{\max} 3 200 (NH) and 2 620 cm⁻¹ (SH); δ (DMSO-d₆) 2.35 (3H, s, CH₃ at position-5 of pyrrole), 2.4 (3H, s, CH₃ at position-3 of pyrrole), 4.4 (2H, br, 2 × SH) and 11.7 (1H, s, NH pyrrole).

2,4-[Di(5-ethylthio-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)]-3,5-dimethylpyrrole : A mixture of 4 (0.29 g; 0.001 mol), anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.56 g, 0.004 mol), ethyl iodide (0.31 g, 0.002 mol) and dry acetone (50 ml) was refluxed for 7 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, treated with water and the separated thioether was filtered washed with water and crystallised from ethanol, (0.21 g, 62%), m.p. 156-58° (Found : C, 47.9; H, 4.5; N, 19.4. C₁₄H₁₇N₅O₂S₂ calcd. for : C, 47.8; H, 4.8; N, 19.9%); ν_{\max} 3 350 cm⁻¹(NH).

2,4-[Di(4-acetyl-5-thio-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)]-3,5-dimethylpyrrole : A mixture of 4 (0.29 g; 0.001 mol) and acetic anhydride (3 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and the separated solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol, (0.32 g, 86%), m.p. 246-48° (Found : C, 44.4; H, 3.7; N, 18.3. C₁₄H₁₃N₅O₄S₂ calcd. for : C, 44.3; H, 3.4; N, 18.4%); ν_{\max} 3 300 (NH), 1 730 (C=O), 1 720 (C=O) and 1 450 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ (DMSO-d₆) 2.35 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.45 (6H, s, 2 × CH₃CO) and 11.7 (1H, s, NH pyrrole); *m/z* 379 (4.57%, M⁺).

2-(5-Mercapto-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-4-(4-amino-5-thio-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)-3,5-dimethylpyrrole (5). Method A : A mixture of 4 (2.95 g; 0.01 mol), hydrazine (95%; 2 ml, 0.04 mol) and absolute ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 8 h. The reaction mixture was filtered, washed with ethanol (10 ml), the combined filtrate and washing was concentrated and cooled to obtain 5, (0.37 g, 12%), m.p. 285°d. The residue of the reaction mixture (2.6 g) had the same m.p., m.m.p. and finger-prints in the ir spectra as 4 in 84% yield.

Method B : A mixture of 4 (2.95 g; 0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (95%; 2 ml, 0.04 mol) in dry diox-

ane (50 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture was then diluted with cold H₂O (100 ml), acidified with concentrated HCl and filtered. The resulting solid was washed with a minimum amount of cold water and crystallised from 1 : 1 ethanol-water to yield **5** (1.9 g 61%), m.p. 285°d (Found : C, 38.9; H, 3.6; N, 31.7. C₁₀H₁₁N₇OS₂ calcd. for : C, 38.8; H, 3.5; N, 31.7%); ν_{\max} 3 350–3 150 (NH, NH₂) and 2 610 cm⁻¹ (SH); δ (DMSO-d₆) 2.35 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.3 (1H, br, SH), 5.6 (2H, s, NH₂), 8.6 (1H, s, NH triazole) and 11.7 (1H, s, NH pyrrole).

Schiff bases of 2-(5-mercapto-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-4-(4-amino-5-thioxo-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)-3,5-dimethylpyrrole (6) : A mixture of equimolar amount (0.002 mol) of **5** and the appropriate aldehyde was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (20 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 h, cooled and filtered. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (yield 74.80%) (Table 1).

2-(4-Benzoyl-5-thioxo-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-4-(4-benzamido-5-thioxo-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)-3,5-dimethyl-

pyrrole (7) : A mixture of **5** (0.3 g; 0.001 mol), benzoyl chloride (0.28 g; 0.002 mol) and dry pyridine (10 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. It was then diluted with cold water (50 ml) and the resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from benzene, (0.35 g, 70%), m.p. 190–92° (Found : C, 55.2, H, 3.9; N, 18.4. C₂₄H₁₉N₇O₃S₂ calcd. for : C, 55.7; H, 3.6; N, 18.9%); ν_{\max} 3 400–3 200 (NH), 1 680 (C=O, N-acyl) and 1 660 cm⁻¹ (C=O amide).

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